

STORY ABOUT SELECTIVE SPEAKING (SELECTIVE MUTISM) APPLICABILITY OF THERAPY (NARRATIVE)

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Abstract

Narrative therapy (NT), which is one of the postmodern therapy methods; a structured, active, collaborative, and psychoeducational enterprise. NT is a form of counseling that views people as separate from their problems. This allows clients to get some distance from the issue to see how it might be helping them, or protecting them, more than it is hurting them. ("Narrative Therapy | Transformations Counseling - Rockford/Crystal Lake") With this new perspective, individuals feel more empowered to make changes in their thought patterns and behavior and "rewrite" their life story for a future that reflects who they are, what they are capable of, and what their purpose is, separate from their problems . ("Therapeutic Tools — Anna Redgrave") The therapist does not function as the expert, but rather helps clients see how they are the experts regarding their own life and, as such, can uncover the dreams, values, goals, and skills that define who they really are, separate from their problems . ("Narrative Therapy | Psychology Today") "These are the buried stories that can be rewritten and woven into the ongoing and future story of their lives." ("Narrative Therapy - thebeachpsychotherapy.com") Selective mutism is also a story surrounded by phenomena such as anxiety disorder or social anxiety. In this thesis, in this thesis, I researched what can be done about selective mutism with NT. NT was successful in selective mutism at the end of my research. These results are not a comparison of other therapy modalities.

Keywords: *Speech and Language Disorders, Narrative Therapy, Selective Mutism*

Introduction

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The therapy process is a process in which the person's feelings, thoughts, and perspective on life are evaluated, and in the same direction, the person's beliefs and attitudes about himself and others are discussed in the company of a specialist. Therapy is an exploratory process that enables the unconscious driving forces to be realized by the individual in daily life without even realizing it, by realizing a communication process through the relations established by the person with both himself and the outside world.

As the most basic principle in the therapy process, dysfunctional and unhealthy thoughts are replaced with alternative/realistic thoughts.

In this change in NT; It seeks to

understand experiences and their understanding.

It puts the client's knowledge at the center.

It takes reference from the speeches of the client.

It seeks the exceptional so that the general does not mislead.

Emphasizes specific personal information.

Searches for specific details of identity and life.

Values personal experience. It encourages people to get to know themselves. It empowers people to live the lives they choose.

Therapy enables the person to explain himself with the guidance of a specialist and in this way to re-evaluate and discover his self. In this respect, we can list the benefits of therapy as follows;

With the practice of therapy, the person feels stronger in the face of difficulties. can feel.

By explaining themselves, people recreate the behaviors that hinder their development. they can evaluate, recognize, and thus change.

Today, many diverse types of therapy are applied, including family and group members.

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Through therapy, the person can change existing negative thought patterns about himself. can address.

While the cognitive aspect of the approaches focuses on creating positive values and belief patterns about their lives, the behavioral aspect focuses on the development of the competence to make healthy choices. (“Download Basics of Counselling Course - SoftArchive”)

Telling has a fundamental task to overcome. When the person tells, he tries to transcend.

In this respect, a person can relieve his past pain through therapy.

Therapy is based on communication with the therapist. For this reason, therapy, communication, and relationship

enabling them to develop their competencies.

Re-evaluation and discovery of oneself through therapy enables them to increase their self-confidence.

Goals for the future are not independent of the evaluation of the current point. In this respect, therapy is an application that enables the determination of future goals.

Therapy, brought about by mental health problems provides coping with symptoms.

Emotions such as fear, anger, grief are extraordinarily strong and difficult to deal with.

The therapy method enables people to cope with these strong emotions. Therapy helps the person to develop their critical thinking skills.

Interpersonal therapy practices, which focus on skills such as communication and relationship building, aim to enable people to express their emotions in a healthy way.

For this purpose, in this study; In individuals experiencing selective mutism and internalizing the problem, whether it is useful to study NT techniques is debated.

1- CHAPTER ONE

1.1. NARRATIVE THERAPY

It is a therapy method that emerged from the work of Michael White and David Epston in the 1980s. The ideas of thinkers such as Michael Foucault, Erving Goffman and Gregory Bateson are influential based on this approach. Foucault's theory of the connection between knowledge and power processes has been fundamentally affected.

NT has a structure that puts the individual on the main axis. "Individuals are born into the world in the written world order.

income and it is exceedingly rare for individuals to realize this phenomenon. (Michael Foucault)

NT is a postmodern therapy. Every life experience represents a story for the individual.

The biggest limiting factor for the individual in original stories is his interaction with the environment. When the counselee thinks that there are certain problems in himself when he thinks that he should get help from a professional, and takes a step back, he suppresses the problem and causes him to take it to further dimensions.

He stated that putting these assumptions at the center of the therapy is important for the solution. Because words affect life directly. How we use these words is therefore a critical issue. Every word used has a positive or negative effect on our lives. Therefore, the change of language is also the change of life.

one

Foucault; that people influence their dominant ideology in the story they have. tells. That is why basic assumptions and stereotypes prevent one from seeing the root cause.

It is essential for the client to be unique and special.

Therefore, rather than the social causes of the events, individual and social looked at their relationship.

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1.2. ASSUMPTIONS OF NARRATIVE THERAPY

The self is not treated as an independent construct but within the context of the relationship. Therefore, he does not prefer individualism in the process of understanding people and their problems.

On the other hand, we can list the assumptions as follows;

NT is a point of view, but it also has certain core applications in helping people. These are called maps. It is called a map because the terrain is always different from the map. In other words, maps are used to guide the application according to the needs of the person.

Basic assumptions;

The problem is just the problem. (A MASA is sometimes just a MASA). From the same point of view, the INDIVIDUAL is only the INDIVIDUAL. Therefore, we cannot see people as a problem.

Problems do not always arise, and they do not always attract our attention. Lifetime influences how we view our experiences. That is why it changes sometimes.

Problems are constructed with cultural contexts. Culture also directly affects the problems. There is no single truth. There are multiple truths. What matters is how we find these truths.

People, of course, know better about their own lives. Of course, they know themselves better.

Therefore, they naturally have all the abilities to help themselves.

Ian Brookes et al., "Chambers Concise Dictionary," Edinburgh: Chambers Harrap Publishers, 2004, p. 789.

The consultant does not see himself as an expert or an authority.

The therapeutic relationship is the main source of change in the therapy process.

The person is the actor of his own life, he is also the author.

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Stories written/told by people about life, that is, their own life stories, it is a projection of their world.

NT sees people's lives in a multi-layered structure. Also, according to him nor is it possible to include all their life stories in a single dominant story line.

NT has the idea that there is no objective reality, that all acts of knowing are just “interpretations” and that people construct existing realities themselves.²

1.3. PEOPLE INSPIRED BY NARRATIVE THERAPY

White and Epston have created narrative therapy in a different and independent way by gathering a multidisciplinary structure such as philosophy, psychology, anthropology, sociology, and much linguistics in a single hand.

With the application they call externalization, White and Epston aim to objectify the problem and save the person from the problem.

Known as the symbolic anthropologist, Cillerper Chip introduced two concepts as expert knowledge and local knowledge. Expert knowledge is mostly seen as the knowledge of the person being consulted.

Local knowledge is the knowledge of the person who experienced the event. Symbolic anthropologist

Cleper Chip added other concepts to NT. These concepts are; superficial description and rich description are two opposite concepts.

Superficial description is a structure in which dominant stories are more common.

In the rich description, it is aimed to see the client through the eyes of the client. It is a concept in which the individuals who experienced the event also make sense of the meaning they experience.

The main event should be accepted as human and the preferred story should be diversified.

Compared with modernism, which emphasizes concepts such as order, absolute reality, purity, and analytical abstraction, postmodernism; complexity, pluralism, diversity and towards inclusiveness. (Dyck, 2000)

Many concepts such as "opposite/negative (silenced) explanation", "differentiation in the therapeutic context", "pressure" that Micheal White, one of the pioneers of narrative therapy, brought to therapy were borrowed from Geragory Bateson. (Dyck, 2000)

Another person who made important contributions to narrative therapy is Edward Bruner. According to Bruner, people learn about life through experiences and derive meaning from their lives through stories or stories (Monk, 1996; Zimmerman & Dickerson, 1994).

Another influential figure in narrative therapy is Michel Foucoult. white and

Epston's concept of "dominant discourses" is derived from Focoult's idea of power and knowledge.

The effect of dominant discourses or social beliefs and norms on the majority population has been managed very skillfully and it is very difficult to notice this effect by the mentioned population.

Individuals adopt many social discourses without questioning as if they are their own ideas and lead their lives without realizing how these discourses affect their lives. These views of Foucolut led White and Epston to develop the idea of the "structural solution" and the "segregation of dogmatically accepted norms and realities that had an overwhelming impact on society". (Dyck, 2000).

2 Firat, "Narrative Therapy as a Postmodern Therapy in Social Work", p. 333

1.4. EXTERNALIZATION

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The ability to comprehend emotional and intellectual processes such as beliefs, intentions, motivations in one's own and others, to associate them with each other and to act accordingly is defined as mentalization.

When the individual encounters problems

mentalization, ability to describe oneself and events may be weakened.

It may be difficult for the individual to see the problem he is facing while living in it, just like in the mirror example. The further you keep the mirror from yourself, the better you will see yourself.

When many people think of NT, the first thing that comes to mind is externalizing conversations.

Externalization is opposed to internalizing problems. In this application, the basic philosophy is shaped by the idea that 'The person is not the problem, the problem itself is the problem'. That is, externalization is categorizing problems, problems experienced, rather than labeling and classifying people.

The person internalizes some negative patterns by saying 'I am depressed, inadequate'.

The main purpose is to get away from the problem that the person internalizes and ascribe to himself, from the beliefs caused by it, and to separate that problem from the identity of the person.

Thus, the person gets away from the shame imposed on his identity. On the other hand, instead of saying "this is how I am" to the problems he is experiencing, he can take responsibility and get to work to take his life away from these problems.

This enables the individual to have a healthy mentalization with the facts in his life and to evaluate his relationship with the problems differently.

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The main purpose of the NT interviews is to keep the determinations in the press stories confidential. to explore aspects. In addition, its basic principle is that “people have many stories.”

1.5. NARRATIVE THERAPY BENEFITS

Among the studies on children, the study of Seymour and Epston is remarkable in terms of NT.

They analyzed the results by applying NT on 45 children diagnosed with kleptomania. As a result of the therapy they applied, they observed positive behavioral changes in children.

Researchers have reported that 80% of children quit stealing completely or to a considerable extent.

Vromans and Schweitzer found that NT performed on 47 adults with major depressive disorder was effective in reducing the symptoms of depression. After a 3-month application, they observed an improvement of 74% in patients with major depressive disorder.³

It was observed that the scores of the adolescents in the experimental group, in which the NT-based group counseling program was applied, obtained from the State-Trait Anxiety Inventory were significantly lower than those in the control group. In addition, contrary to expectations, no significant difference was found between the self-regulation skills of the experimental and control groups.

As a result of the study, it was determined that narrative therapy provided a significant decrease in anxiety scores, but no difference was observed in terms of willpower (Koca 2018).

L. Vromans, R. Schweitzer, “Narrative Therapy for Adults with a Major Depressive Disorder: Improved

Symptom and Interpersonal Outcomes,” *Psychotherapy Research*, p. 21 (2011), p. 4-15, doi:10.1080/10503301003591792.

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In a similar study conducted with adolescents, it was found that the psychological resilience scores of the participants in the narrative therapy group were higher than the control group, and the therapy gains continued to be preserved in the follow-up measurement made approximately 4 months later.

These results show that narrative therapy is effective in strengthening resilience in adolescents. points out that it can be useful (Yazıçý 2018).

In a study examining the effectiveness of narrative therapy on depression and loneliness symptoms, it was found that the depression and loneliness scores of the participants in the therapy group were significantly lower than the control group (Dastbaaz et al. 2014; cited in Akkuş et al., 2020).

Another study compared the effectiveness of narrative therapy and cognitive behavioral therapy (CBT) in individuals with depression. As a result of the study, it was determined that both therapy methods significantly reduced depressive symptoms (Lopes et al. 2014a; cited by Akkuş et al., 2020).

2- SECTION TWO

2.1. LANGUAGE AND SPEECH DISORDERS

In the post-modern approach, language is an element that reveals mental phenomena.

Freud said, "There is no language process, there is a brain slip." The phrase (see Parafraz) also draws attention to an unconscious aspect of language.

Language and speech disorders, which express problems in one or both skills of understanding spoken words and expressing oneself, appear in many forms.

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interest.

For example;

Delayed language and speech: The age of the child's receptive and expressive language skills
It is a situation where it does not show progress at the expected level.

Articulation (pronunciation) and phonological (phonological) disorders: It is a language and
speech problem in which the speaker pays attention to how he says rather than what he says
because of the person's incorrect production of speech sounds, syllables, or words.

Fluency problems (stuttering, tachypemia – cluttering): It is a speech problem in which the
fluency, rhythm and speed of speech are affected.

Voice disorders: It is a disorder in which one or more of the pitch, intensity or quality of the
voice attracts more attention than what the speaker is saying due to assorted reasons.

Aphasia (Acquired language disorders): It is a neurological origin language and speech disorder
that occurs due to an acquired damage to the brain.

Swallowing Disorders: It is the difficulty in swallowing that develops mostly due to a
neurological cause and is seen at various stages of swallowing.

Motor speech disorders: These are disorders in which the speech mechanism is affected because
of weakness, weakness and coordination disorder in the muscle groups required for speech due
to a neurological cause.

Language and speech are two different concepts that are often confused in daily life. Language
and speech- related disorders are also different from each other.

In the study, selective mutism was chosen from these DK problems. The most important reason
for this is that individuals with selective mutism can express themselves if there is no relevant
problematic aspect.

2.2. LANGUAGE AND SPEAKING DIFFICULTY

Language and speech difficulties; the presence of disorder in the flow, rhythm, treble, emphasis, extraction of phonemes, articulation, articulation and meaning of speech; It is the situation where the difficulties in using language, acquiring speech and communication due to the disruptions and irregularities that occur at different levels and forms in verbal communication negatively affect the educational performance and social adaptation of the individual.

Speech; It is a motor process related to the structure and functions of organs, muscles and nerves that allow speech. In case of any disorder in the structure or functions of these organs, muscles and nerves, the child has difficulty in making sounds or cannot express them correctly because they cannot use these organs, even if they know the structure and features of the language.

2.3. SELECTIVE MUTISM (SELECTIVE SPEAKING)

Selective Mutism (SM) is the state of speaking in an environment of one's own choosing. In addition, as

it is an anxiety state disorder, it often accompanies social anxiety. The individual avoids talking sometimes because he is ashamed and sometimes because he is afraid. Sometimes a cause cannot be found. Although the individual speaks in other situations, they prefer not to speak in situations where there is an expectation of speaking from them. Its incidence in the population is approximately 1%.

SM emerges from childhood. People usually knock on the door with such complaints.

SM; It is the persistent inability to speak in specific social situations in which it is expected to speak, despite speaking in other situations. The time of emergence and persistence of this problem is at least one month. Children may choose not to talk because they are often embarrassed when they first start school. However, if the child's behavior of not speaking continues in the future, precautions should be taken in this regard.

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In such cases, many different disciplines such as family, siblings, school counselors, classroom teachers, course teachers, language and speech therapists should work in cooperation, rather than just collaborating with the individual.

SM encompasses different schools due to past diagnoses. Therefore, they need to be supported by the family and the teacher. It disappears with multimodal approaches such as behavioral therapy, cognitive behavioral therapy, play therapy, family therapy.

Disturbances in language and speech do not only affect the speaking process. It also affects the life process of the child. Failure to notice such situations causes the child to become more withdrawn. For this reason, it may cause him to feel inadequate and to give up talking completely.

SM is an anxiety disorder in which a person is not normally able to talk in certain situations, in certain places, or with certain people if triggered. Selective mutism often coexists with social anxiety disorder.⁴

People with selective mutism experience the consequences of their silence as embarrassment, social exclusion, or punishment.

Even so, they remain silent.

Vienna (2009). "Selective mutism: A review and integration of the last 15 years". Clinical Psychology Review. 29

(1): 57-67. doi:10.1016/j.cpr.2008.09.009. PMID 18986742.

2.4. TECHNIQUES APPLIED IN SELECTIVE MUTISM

Behavioral approaches are the most frequently used intervention methods with a strong scientific orientation.

When we look at the successful methods, there are behavioral techniques such as stimulus extinction, systematic desensitization, reinforcement, and response elicitation.

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(Harris, 1996)

Gradual Approach: We give reinforcement to the verbal behaviors of the individual.

We do not reward nonverbal behavior. So, we help dampen the behavior.

Self-Modelling: Video footage is taken of the individual in positive situations about himself, his speech, and skills. These images are then shown to the person. Thus, it is aimed to encourage the person who sees himself talking.

Mysterious Motivator: It is a method that increases the expectation and rewarding of the individual.

It is a secret rewarding process. It is used in activities within the group. For example, when the individual speaks or speaks, the consultant gives an oral or written reward.

Response Arousal: It is a model that works in reverse. The day before, the child is given the message that he needs to talk to the therapist. The individual will either talk to the therapist or spend time with them all day.

3- CHAPTER THREE

3.1. EXTERNALIZATION OF EMOTIONS AND THOUGHTS FROM THE PROBLEM OF SELECTIVE MUTISM WITH NARRATIVE THERAPY

Therapists using a narrative approach aim to disrupt and change the way the client speaks, which ensures the persistence of the problem. Using the questioning process, therapists create opportunities for clients to explore various aspects of their own life situations.

Externalization is opposed to internalizing problems. In this application, the basic philosophy is shaped by the idea that 'The person is not the problem, the problem itself is the problem'.

Story therapists believe that people's identities are shaped by the stories they tell about their lives.

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When these stories focus on specific problems, the person often begins to see the problem as part of themselves.

However, story therapy sees people's problems outside of the individual and tries to organize the stories people tell about themselves in a way that allows them to see their problems that way as well.

The stance of narrative therapy is quite different from many other forms of therapist-led therapy.

It can be uncomfortable and takes a lot of practice for clients to successfully detach themselves from their problems.

As the negative story becomes dominant in his mind, new events that fit the story (like someone calling him to spend time with him) will be privileged over other events that do not fit the story.

These events can be transferred as a coincidence or anomaly.

The story therapist's goal is to collaborate with the individual to create an alternative story that better suits what they really want from their life. There are several techniques commonly used by story therapists to do this.

Before coming to studies that these techniques will be beneficial in selective mutism, First I should add that the externalized element is an externalization of concerns.

Because the idea behind this technique is that if we see our problems as an integral part of our personality, the change of these negativities may be impossible. ("What Is Narrative Therapy? Definition and Techniques") However, if these problems are something the individual does, he may blame himself more.

It is often difficult for clients to adopt this perspective.

However, doing so can empower the person and make people feel like they have more control over their problems.

Let us think about a person who has a lot of anxiety problems. This person defines himself as a worried person now that he has internalized the problem he is experiencing up to a point.

This is mentally and emotionally painful for them, but also physically exhausting.

Externalization indicates that one can go to the solution without being a part of the situation.

“We fail because we try to find solutions to the wrong problems rather than the wrong solutions to problems.” (Russell L. Ackoff)

The benefits of externalizing are:

More control. Gain greater self-control while managing symptoms and problems. When a person internalizes the symptom or problem, they may feel as if they have completely lost control of what is happening to them. Taking a unique perspective improves their ability to manage their problems.

According to narrative therapy, how people will feel about a situation and how

What determines whether they will act depends on how that person makes sense of and interprets the situation in his own way.

In narrative therapy, the situation created by the problem is nothing more than a created social reality that is sustained through problem behaviors and coordinated in language. That is, people have centralized their problems in social constructivist metaphors.

Created social realities reveal themselves in the stories they develop to both construct the identity value of the individual and to make sense of their relations with others. From this perspective, individuals are “meaning makers;” and this meaning is the main element that both shapes and limits people's perspectives (Payne, 2006).

Emotional balance. Relief by saying one's problems aloud and then feeling more peaceful. When they are more emotionally stable, it will be much easier to observe the problem from a unique perspective.

Added resources to solve the problem. Problem solving is often not easy.

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Externalization enables a person to take advantage of added resources to better solve their process. New tools become opportunities for innovative solutions.

Being able to take more responsibility for problems. If the person feels overwhelmed by their difficulties, they often lose control of the situation. (“Externalization: A Way to Get Away from Your Problems”) Externalization allows them to take responsibility for the things they can change and act more easily.

Changing and questioning beliefs. Some preconceived ideas may hinder rather than help. This technique opens a person to create new ways of thinking.

Maintaining the distance between the problem and the person. Externalization makes it easier for a person to expand or change their perspective. (“Externalization: Get Away From Your Problems | lifeaws.com”) Thanks to this, they can move away from the identity they identify with themselves and dislike.

Thus, language has ceased to be a tool for expression and is considered as a tool for people to use culture and language (Vollmer, 2000).

According to Rosen and Lang (2005), while the problem is under investigation in narrative therapy,

The following criteria should be considered. These criteria are:

The question should be "what is the problem" rather than "who".

The problem is settled in patterns such as “should” or “...to do/think about.”

The problem has multiple aspects.

Problems arise through discourses embedded in power relations. continues to exist

The problem-focused definition shapes the "dominant story" of the person's current life.

3.2. CREATING A NARRATOR

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The therapist and client work together to tell the client's story in their own words.

In this process, the therapist and client seek various meanings in the story that can help the client change their current story or create new ones.

This process is sometimes referred to as “rewriting” or “re-story making.”

This is based on the idea that a lived event can have many different meanings and interpretations.

In NT, the client will realize that he or she can make new meanings out of his experiences.

Connecting the new story to the past and extending it to the future; The client's new story is associated with past events.

In addition, the client is provided to expand their story into the future.

For this, the counselor's ideas about the future expectation as a strong and talented person are listened to.

“Suppose...,” “What would you do if...,” “assuming...,” “...?” It prompts the individual to imagine alternative ways by asking questions and giving directions that open the door to the discovery of new possibilities.

The view that “people shape the meaning of their lives through the stories that organize their lives” is one of the basic assumptions of narrative therapy. They gain various experiences to express themselves to people, and they share various life stories that have very important effects on the structuring of life.

For people who want to discover the meaning of their lives/experiences and make sense of their lives, creating stories is essential. However, people shape their identities not only through their own experiences, but also through external stories and discourses (gender-related stories formed by social norms and discourses, etc.) (Dyck, 2000).

People reveal their selves in the stories they develop to make sense of and define both their own identities and their social relationships. From this point of view, the being we call human is a

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meaning seeker, descriptor, and constructor. This is a situation that both shapes and limits people.

3.3. DECONSTRUCTION

Reframing a problem means making it more specific to focus on the core of the problem.

When a story has dominated our lives for a long time, we may begin to overgeneralize it and therefore have trouble seeing what the underlying problem really is. For example, the individual has the perception that I am shy and cannot speak.

A story therapist learns what clients really think of the problem they are struggling with.

It allows them to examine the story piece by piece to discover it.

For example, a client may say that she feels frustrated because her family does not value her because she is not wealthy.

This is a very general statement, and it is difficult to develop a solution to this problem. (“What Is Narrative Therapy? Definition and Techniques”)

That is, the therapist asks why he or she creates a narrative in which he is devalued by his family. will collaborate with the client to solve the problem to get an idea.

This can be done by carefully examining details that the client has overlooked.

3.4. UNIQUE ITEMS

This technique consists of looking at one's story from a new perspective/perspective and developing more positive, life-affirming stories as a result. (“What Is Narrative Therapy? Definition and Techniques”)

Since there are many stories, we could potentially talk about our experiences, the point of this technique is to re-imagine our story.

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This way the new story can minimize the problem that has become overwhelming in the old story.

In the therapy setting, it should be considered that everyone's story is unique and unique and should not be judged or ignored in any way, on the contrary, an environment should be created that will ensure that all stories are equally legitimated.

A therapy environment should be created in which clients will have the freedom to tell their own story directly in their own language, without including how others perceive or will perceive their story. This situation requires the client to listen carefully by the therapist and to give the client sufficient time to tell his or her story.

In addition, it is especially important for narrative therapy to accept and approve the fact that clients come to therapy with different stories that create the opportunity to construct more than one story covering their lives (Parry & Doan, 1994).

4. CHAPTER FOUR

4.1. DISCUSSION

Narrative therapy is known to help individuals, couples, and families with problems such as anxiety, depression, explosive disorder, family, and relationship conflict. There are, of course, a few criticisms leveled at narrative therapy, however.

First, because it has existed for a brief time compared to other types of therapy, narrative

There is not a lot of scientific evidence for the therapy's effectiveness.

Additionally, some clients may not be completely truthful when telling their stories. Unless the client is completely honest in creating their story, it is difficult to benefit from therapy.

Moreover, the narrative therapy approach is suitable for those with limited cognitive or language skills or it will not be suitable for individuals who are psychotic.

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However, in problems caused by anxiety disorders such as selective mutism, it is possible to witness

the anxieties of individuals and analyze these feelings by the client, with many methods from speaking to drawing because of the trust to be given to the client.

The client's experiences are emphasized by using a common language with the client. This common language can range from body language to painting.

Since NT is not a neutral practice, the client, and the therapist research together, and because of this research, the client's stories about themselves and life become clearer.

aim to enrich.

In this thesis, the effects of NT theory, which is one of the counseling theories that can be used to develop functional thinking about selective mutism, are emphasized.

During the research process, only three (3) individuals were included in the experimental group of 10 people.

Although the session was held, people caused it to give incredibly positive feedback with selective mutism.

More research is needed on the thesis. In addition, the dwindling number of subjects and sessions is its weak side.

4.2. APPLICATION EXAMPLE

The individual, especially in school life, when his teachers put him on the board

He states that he cannot speak, that cold sweat runs down his forehead and that he is very embarrassed.

For obstructive and negative emotions, the counselor asks the following question;

-If all these negative emotions you felt at that moment were a person or an entity, what would you call it?

-No

-What would you achieve if Hayri left your life?

-I always wanted to be a presenter or to be applauded on stage...

-Then, is not Hayri's existence an obstacle for you?

-Yes!

-What kind of life will you have if he leaves?

-Free!

-Then Hayri is not a part of you; because if you lost a part of yourself – for example, your hand – you would not feel free, would you?

-...

Figure 1

Figure 2

Examples of externalized language use are given below in a comparative way (Payne, 2006):

The language example of traditional therapy approaches, the externalized language examples of narrative therapy;

“Since when do you have nightmares?” In its place; When did these nightmares you speak of begin to appear?

Instead of “You have been alone for most of your life;” Loneliness seems to have accompanied you for most of your life

“You have an obsessive-compulsive personality.” In its place;

You have rituals that make you feel safe and relax

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Instead of “You Are an Alcoholic;”

Alcohol is good at managing your life.

"You're both jealous of each other." In its place;

You and your partner realize that jealousy is invading your relationship?

Narrative therapists have three basic steps in externalizing the problem;

- a) Naming the problem
- ii) Relative impact questions
- iii) suggest that Mapping should be followed. (Payne, 2006)

NT EXAMPLES OF QUESTIONS

1. I wonder if we had a name for this problem you are experiencing, what would you name it?
2. Do you have a special definition to name the situation he is in?
3. The way I see it, there are so many things you have been through - let us clarify and concretize them a bit more shall we?
4. What do you think these experiences are?
5. How can we name these experiences? (Carey & Russell, 2003).
6. I describe the situation you are in as “constructive rejection.” Do you think this term Can it be used to describe their experiences?

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7. How would you describe all these experiences?
8. Did the people around you have an impact on how you define yourself in this way?
9. Have you ever found yourself questioning these definitions?
10. How do you think we can call all these things you told me? (Mascher, 2002)

4.3. TEST

Apart from the pretest and posttest data from the sample, 1-month follow-up data were collected, and measurement tools related to these variables were added to the framework of the study to evaluate the effectiveness of NT on different variables.

4.4. APPLICATION

- A total of ten (10) individuals between the ages of 18-35 with selective mutism were included in the study.

participant was recruited.

- Participants pre-intervention and post-intervention 1-month follow-up evaluated.
- As the data collection tools of the study, one-to-one interview, feedback and observation/monitoring methods and test, questionnaire/question instructions were used. • As feedback, the

participants were provided with an experiment with other participants -for example, if there is a problem of speaking in front of the public-.

- Certificate of achievement was given to all sessions and individuals who participated in the application.

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(NT Therapy Technique)

- As NT Technique, the participants were provided to write therapeutic letters to the cases they externalized.

Therapeutic Letter Writing: The use of writing therapeutic letters has been used quite frequently in therapies (especially in family therapies) in recent years and has found a wide range of use in narrative therapy.

According to White and Epston, this stage in therapy begins with "transformation". This concept represents the transformation of personal meanings and the integration of alternative stories with the client's life (Dyck, 2000).

As a result of Epston's informal research, it has been observed that clients tend to keep letters from therapists as a precious treasure after reading them an average of four times.

Therapeutic documents not only give clients the feeling that they are heard by others, but also enable therapists to find the skills to apply the true beliefs they describe in their letters to clients' lives.

Reinforcing the creation of the new story by accepting and approving the success of the clients during the session and during the use of narrative letters is considered an especially crucial step in narrative therapy (Dyck, 2000).

PERSONAL INFORMATION ABOUT THE STUDY GROUP

AGE: BETWEEN 18-35

NUMBER: 10

AGE 18

NUMBER: 1

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AGE: 22 NUMBER: 2

AGE: 29 NUMBER: 1

AGE: 31 NUMBER: 1

AGE 32 NUMBER: 1

AGE: 33 NUMBER: 1

AGE: 34 NUMBER: 1

AGE: 35 NUMBER: 2

MALE: 5 FEMALES: 5

The way to reach the emotions is expressed as focusing on their cognition (Beck, 2015).

The income status of the families of 6 (six) people is "medium", (30%) 3 (Three) people are good (10%), 1 (One) defined the person as below average.

For the descriptive identification of the participants in the study, information about their age and gender was also presented.

4.5. DATA COLLECTION

As a data collection tool, tests, forms, and questionnaires were used.

Automatic Thoughts Scale

1. Social Threat, 2. Personal Failure, 3.

For each item, the participant was asked to mark how often that item came to mind in the last week.

SENTENCE COMPLETION FORM (ORALLY TAKEN ACCORDING TO AGE)

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1. People
2. My family
3. My close friends
4. My current relationships.....
5. Most of the people in my close circle.....
6. Boys/girls
7. Relationships with the other sex
8. According to others I
9. When in a group.....
10. When you are alone
11. When I compare myself with others
-
12. It worries me the most.
13. When I experience a negative situation, I blame
14. I
15. I have difficulty speaking in person or in situations.

AFTER APPLICATION ***In

Addition to the same test, the following questionnaire was filled.

What is your gender? Woman man

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What is your age?

Response

Your education status?

Middle School

High

School Associate

Licence

Master's/PhD

What is your marital status?

married

Divorced

Wife passed away

How many children do you have ?

Response

What is your reason for applying? Confidence

Anger

Fear

Selective Mutism

Did you participate as a family? Yes

No

Did you benefit from the method you applied?

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I have benefited 1-7

I did not see any benefit 1-7

7 Highest

In which of the sessions did you notice a change in behavior or emotion?

Would you recommend this method for solving problems?

TEST RESULTS

Positive feedback was received in this study.

AUTOMATIC THOUGHT REGISTRATION FORM

Result

1.New Emotion 0-100%

2Automatic

Current Belief in Thought 0-100%

Real-like/

Balanced Thoughts 0-100%

Automatic Thoughts Contrary Evidence Auto Drops 0-100%

Emotion(s) 0-100%

Event/Status Date 110

LIMITATIONS

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1. This study is limited to the data collected from 10(Ten) participants.
2. The subjective well-being and self-confidence approaches in the study are limited to the qualities measured by the scales used in the study.
3. The results of the study; It is limited to the data obtained from the data collection tools to be used in the research.
4. The study has not been compared with other therapy modalities.

CONCLUSION

The following basic hypothesis has been discussed in the study: Narrative Therapy includes techniques that can be applied with a problem such as selective mutism. As a result of the research, it was seen that the hypothesis was confirmed. As a result of the research, it was seen that the anxiety and insecure behavior scores of the participants about not speaking selectively decreased significantly. As a result of the research, it was seen that the participants increased their social, emotional, and behavioral skills.

As a result, all the studies managed in line with the purpose of the research show that different techniques have positive effects on the socio-emotional development of individuals with NT. It is seen that NT approaches can be supported, and integrated education programs can be applied to improve and contribute to

the development of children who do not know the way to express themselves, who cannot express themselves, who have been exposed to trauma or whose socio-emotional skills are weak.

AUTHORS' CONTRIBUTION LEVEL: First author 100%

FINANCIAL SUPPORT: No financial support was received for the study. (“COVID-19 infection during the third trimester of pregnancy: Current ...”)

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST: There is no potential conflict of interest in the study. (“Changes in telomere length and telomerase activity in ... - OUP Academic”)

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